

Original Research

Preparing for Co-Creation: A roadmap for planning a co-creation initiative from a case study on sedentary behaviour in Scottish SMEs – A health CASCADE study

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ABSTRACT

Objective: Co-creation is recognised as a promising approach for addressing complex health issues by collaborating with end-users to develop tailored solutions that meet their needs. Planning a co-creation initiative—resulting in a co-creation protocol—requires balancing between providing clear project details and the need for flexibility in co-creation. However, existing structured guidance necessary for effective co-creation planning in the literature does not exist. This study aimed to develop a practical co-creation planning roadmap for public health researchers and practitioners.

Study design: Iterative development of an evidence-based co-creation planning roadmap based on case study reflections and expert input, and supported by existing co-creation literature.

Methods: The roadmap was developed based on the experience of applying the PRODUCES framework and principles of the planning phase by Leask and colleagues (2019) for planning a co-creation case study on reducing sedentary behaviour in Scottish companies. The roadmap underwent several rounds of iteration with the research team, incorporated feedback from researchers experienced with co-creation, and was further supported by the established evidence base of co-creation literature.

Results: The resulting roadmap has a seven-step approach, divided into four sections, involving: whether and why co-creation is an appropriate approach, framing the co-creation initiative (Section 1: Identify), defining stakeholders and co-creator sampling, describing resources and outcomes (Section 2: Define), structuring co-creation sessions, selecting methods for the co-creation sessions (Section 3: Structure) and planning for evaluation (Section 4: Plan Evaluation).

Conclusion: The roadmap offers a structured and accessible process to guide the planning of co-creation initiatives. We suggest that the roadmap be applied to different contexts to further refine and validate its utility, with the ultimate goal of enhancing the systematic planning of co-creation in public health.

1. Introduction

Complex health issues, like sedentary behaviour (SB), are deeply ingrained in daily habits and influenced by social, political, and economic factors.^{1,2} Traditional top-down interventions often fail to address these complexities effectively because they overlook the perspectives and lived experiences of the individuals they seek to influence.^{3,4} This has led to growing advocacy for bottom-up approaches and

greater end-user involvement.^{3,4} Collaborative approaches, such as co-design, co-production, and co-creation, focus on working together with multiple stakeholders and making decisions collectively. In this paper, co-creation is utilised, defined as the continuous active collaboration and shared decision-making among various stakeholders towards creative problem-solving covering all initiative phases, from problem identification to evaluation.^{5,6} To clarify, co-creation encompasses co-design—where stakeholders collaborate to develop solutions to

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Fig. 1. The PRODUCES framework, stages and principles of co-creation by Leask and colleagues³ as illustrated by Health Cascade^{22,23} (Licensed under CC BY 4.0).

defined problems—and co-production—which involves their participation in implementing agreed-upon solutions.⁷ Co-creation leads to tailored solutions that meet the needs of the end-users.^{3,8,9} As a result, the solutions may be more effective and sustainable with an impact on public health.^{8–10}

Planning a co-creation initiative results in a co-creation protocol—a structured yet flexible plan outlining co-creation implementation and evaluation. A co-creation protocol must balance providing clear project details with flexibility. It must be adaptable to input from co-creators and allow adjustments during real-world implementation, such as changes in methods or session formats.^{11,12} Currently, the structured, comprehensive guidance required to plan a co-creation protocol effectively and with rigour does not exist. There are some co-creation protocols in public health research,^{13–16} and recent publications offer guidance for planning co-creation initiatives.^{17,18} Grey literature offers valuable practical insights but often lacks peer review or empirical validation desired for application in research contexts.^{19–21} Leask and colleagues³ outline key principles for co-creating public health interventions (Fig. 1). Within the first stage, ‘planning’, they proposed the PRODUCES framework as a systematic structure to frame the co-creation study’s aim, one of their key principles. Although these principles provided a strong foundation for co-creation, they were not designed as a comprehensive guide for planning an entire co-creation initiative. Building on the PRODUCES framework and principles, we developed a practical co-creation planning roadmap for public health practitioners and researchers.

2. Methods

The roadmap was developed based on reflections on planning and running a specific co-creation study (hereafter referred to as the case study). In the methods, we describe the background and planning

approach for the case study and the methods used to develop the roadmap (Fig. 2).

2.1. Case study background

The case study was a co-creation initiative focused on addressing high levels of workplace SB. The aim was to co-create a solution for implementation in the workplace with office-based employees in small to medium enterprises (SMEs) in Glasgow. The study was part of Health CASCADE, a European-funded initiative to establish evidence-based co-creation methodologies,²² which provided a network of expert advisors, cross-project learning, and research secondments.

2.2. Case study planning approach

The planning approach was an iterative process involving repeated revisions. It first utilised the ‘planning’ phase from Leask and colleagues,³ (Fig. 1) to frame the study’s aim using the PRODUCES framework and identify the appropriate sampling strategy. Other phases (‘conducting’, ‘evaluating’, ‘reporting’) provided additional insight into key elements of co-creation. Additional resources were sought through a pragmatic literature search and expert input to enrich the planning approach. The literature search focused on best practices and guidance, particularly relevant to UK workplaces,^{19,24,25} using databases like PubMed, Google and the Health CASCADE database (—a consolidation of scientific articles about co-creation).²⁶ Collaboration with co-creation experts from the Health CASCADE network further enriched the planning approach by offering advice on applying the PRODUCES framework and tailoring planning decisions to the initiative. Insights from a facilitation expert at Health CASCADE partner 3KQ (a facilitation and evaluation consultancy firm) emphasised the importance of facilitation and resource preparation. The researcher’s (Mi.V.) previous internship

Fig. 2. Methods for planning the co-creation case study and developing the co-creation planning roadmap.

experience in the collaborative development of health policy in Belgian companies added valuable real-world perspectives.

2.3. Development of the roadmap

The roadmap for co-creation planning was developed based on the experience and approach to planning and running the case study, informed by expert input, and further supported by the established evidence base of co-creation literature. The roadmap underwent several iterations with the research team (all authors) and incorporated one round of feedback from six researchers at Ghent University experienced in co-creation. The roadmap was finalised when the research team agreed that the case study planning approach and the Ghent University researchers’ considerations were fully reflected in its steps. Each step of the roadmap is explained in the results and illustrated using the case study as a practical example.

3. Results

The co-creation planning roadmap comprises seven steps across four sections (Fig. 3). Although presented in a structured order for clarity, the planning process is likely iterative and non-linear, with multiple revisions of previous steps anticipated.

3.1. Section 1 - Identify

3.1.1. Step I - Need for co-creation

A preliminary step in co-creation planning is assessing whether co-creation is an appropriate approach, given the considerable time and resources required.²⁷ This involves identifying and understanding the

problem, its complexities (e.g., root causes and contextual factors), and the potential benefits of involving stakeholders. Consulting decision-making tools for co-creation^{17,21,28} and expert advice can aid in deciding if co-creation is appropriate. For the case study, the need to address SB among Scottish office workers and the potential for applying a co-creation methodology was determined beforehand by experienced co-creation and SB researchers, including Ma.V. and P.D., for the initial Health CASCADE²² funding application. Mi.V. validated this need by reviewing literature, highlighting the complexity of workplace habits and the limited effectiveness of traditionally developed interventions.^{29,30} While experienced researchers can recognise the need for a solution through field experience or evidence review,³¹ stakeholders’ support for the identified problem is essential. Ideally, stakeholders with direct experience with the issue should initiate or be involved in problem formulation and assessing whether a co-creation approach is warranted.

3.1.2. Step II - Frame the co-creation initiative

This step aligns with a key principle from Leask and colleagues,³ focused on refining the initiative’s aim. Question frameworks, e.g., PICO (Problem(P), Intervention(I), Comparison(C), and Outcome (O))³²—commonly used for systematic reviews in medicine³³—facilitate concise problem definition by clearly identifying the essential information required to frame it, thereby promoting transparency and focus.³ Similarly, the PRODUCES framework has been proposed as a question framework tailored for co-creation planning in public health.³ Using this framework introduces a structured, systematic approach to planning, improving transparency with co-creators, reducing the risk of ambiguity and contributing to generating scientifically trustworthy evidence.³ Using the PRODUCES framework in the case study proved a valuable,

Fig. 3. Roadmap for planning a co-creation initiative.

Table 1Illustration of the PRODUCES framework³ to the co-creation case study for the development of a solution to reduce occupational sitting among SME employees.

PRODUCES	Guiding question	Case description
Problem Objective	What is the reason for the process? What is the aim of the process?	The prevalent issue of high amounts of sedentary behaviour among office workers in the workplace The co-creation process aims to create a solution with employees to reduce occupational sitting and empower them to drive positive change within their workplaces.
Design (end-)Users	What specific participatory methodology is used for co-creation? Who will use the co-created intervention?	A participatory action research approach ³⁴ is adopted, emphasising iterative cycles of action, evaluation, and reflection to fine-tune the co-creation process and have it result in a tailored solution. The end-users are office workers from Scottish SMEs. The focus on SMEs is driven by their high diversity, necessitating tailored solutions, and the resource constraints often faced by these entities.
Co-creators	Who is engaging in the process?	An action group of employees will collaborate as co-creators, with researchers as facilitators. A planning group, including the primary company contact and several employees with a broad and relevant overview of the company, will contribute input and feedback on the co-creation initiative.
Evaluation	How is success measured?	Evaluation will include both process and impact assessments. The process assessment will include the engagement and attendance of co-creators, as well as the continuity of the action group after the sessions. Another researcher (L. McC.) will conduct interviews after the sessions to explore the co-creators' experience of the co-creation. ³⁵ Formative evaluations will involve gathering co-creators' feedback and facilitators' reflections after each session. A focus group, conducted after a three-month implementation phase, will capture the co-creators' perspectives on the strengths and weaknesses of the co-creation process, as well as the extent to which the co-created solution has been implemented. To assess the impact, we will examine changes in the target behaviour among both co-creators and all employees within the company.
Scalability	How can the solution be scaled to a population level?	The co-creation process will be conducted in three different SMEs. The refined co-creation process can then be replicated in future projects - with adaptations made to suit the new context - to produce tailored solutions.

albeit iterative, exercise, with answers often revisited as planning evolved (Table 1). Ideally, the framework should be completed by the end of planning to guide the co-creation initiative.

3.2. Section 2 - Define

3.2.1. Step III - Define stakeholders and co-creator sampling

This step involves identifying stakeholders and determining who will act as co-creators. Stakeholders are individuals, groups, or entities interested in the initiative's outcomes.³⁶ Essential considerations include (1) Who are the key stakeholders, and which should participate as co-creators; (2) What is an appropriate sample size of stakeholders to engage as co-creators; (3) What is an appropriate approach for sampling stakeholders to engage as co-creators; (4) What are effective strategies for contacting and recruiting stakeholders as co-creators. These decisions impact the initiative's structure, resource allocation and formation of the action group—a collective of co-creators who collaborate continuously, produce knowledge and make shared decisions to create, adapt, or refine a solution.

The initial focus is on identifying stakeholders with essential perspectives, knowledge, and skills needed for co-creating solutions to the problem.³⁷ The case study, for instance, identified SME owners, HR staff, managers, and employees as key stakeholders. However, involving all these groups in co-creation may not always be feasible or beneficial due to potential conflicts or power dynamics.²⁴ Employing methods such as MapStakes or network mapping and analysis provide a systematic approach to mapping stakeholders for co-creation, offering insights into the dynamics of a network.^{18,38} Determining the sample size for the action group can be challenging due to a lack of clear guidelines. The appropriate size depends on available resources and the initiative's context while ensuring diversity in stakeholder knowledge, characteristics, and perspectives. The case study set a target sample size of 10–12, as it facilitates interactive discussions and group work while accounting for potential dropouts due to high workloads.^{3,39,40} The sampling approach should ensure diversity and essential expertise are represented.³ Purposeful sampling techniques - intentionally selecting participants with specific, relevant characteristics - can support this.^{3,41} For the case study, quota sampling was selected to ensure representation by selecting a fixed number of co-creators from each workplace department.⁴² However, convenience sampling—selection based on accessibility—was used as a backup to secure engagement and commitment.^{3,41,43,44} Finally, it is important to select appropriate and likely various recruitment strategies.³⁷ This includes identifying suitable channels, organisations, and gatekeepers, along with outlining

expectations and the initiative's relevance and potential benefits to support recruitment.^{37,45} The case study recruited SMEs through local health networks, social media (e.g., LinkedIn), cold emailing, and a dedicated website. Employee recruitment to the action group was leveraged by internal communications via our internal contact person in that SME.

Stakeholder involvement is critical at every co-creation stage, including the planning of the co-creation initiative. The questions above—whom to involve, how many to engage, and how to reach them—are also relevant when preparing to involve stakeholders early in planning. This often results in forming a planning group—a collective of stakeholders who provide input, feedback, and support. Early involvement enhances, for instance, contextual relevance by leveraging their understanding of key stakeholders. In the case study, stakeholder input during planning was lacking; however, SME employee planning groups were established before implementation, supporting the initiative.

3.2.2. Step IV - Describe resources and outcomes

This step maps resources and anticipates outcomes for the co-creation initiative, benefiting from structured approaches like logic models to identify gaps and ensure feasibility. Resource preparation considers human, material, and informational resources and practical concerns like costs, to prevent implementation failures and assess the initiative's viability.³¹ Anticipating outcomes focuses on broader changes in attitudes, behaviours, policies, or practices and includes reflection on their achievability, value, and sustainability.^{46,47}

The terminology of 'resources' and 'outcomes' comes from logic modelling—a planning tool that aims to, often visually, capture how a project hopes to work.⁴⁸ A logic model was created during the planning of the case study (Supplementary Material 2), offering a valuable and accessible tool to map the co-creation initiative from beginning to end, clarifying links between what is done, what is expected to happen and the resources needed to make it happen. Its value in co-creation lies not in rigid application—since co-creation is non-linear and requires adaptability—but in the iterative reflection its development encourages.⁴⁸ The logic model can also provide a framework for evaluation (i.e., evaluating the impact of the co-creation process and solution).⁴⁹

Resource considerations prioritise careful facilitator selection and training. Logistical decisions, like holding sessions online or in person, shape resource requirements and depend on location, space, technology, and participants' skill levels. The co-creation process can be seen as a potential intervention; therefore, outcomes may be included for both the target group of the solution and the co-creators themselves, such as skill-building.⁵⁰ It is also important to become familiar with potential

external influences, like the culture, political environment, or co-creators’ circumstances (e.g., students’ moods during exams⁵¹) to avoid unintended consequences.⁴⁶ Staying updated on research, clear community partner communication, and considering systemic barriers supports this.⁵²

3.3. Section 3 - Structure

3.3.1. Step V - Structure the co-creation sessions

This step involves structuring the co-creation process by planning the sequence and objectives of sessions to create, refine, or adapt a solution that meets the initiative’s aim. Unclear objectives can cause confusion and complicate facilitation;⁵¹ therefore, clear planning is essential for transparency and co-creators’ engagement. Additionally, ethical or funding bodies may require detailed session plans.¹¹

There is no one-size-fits-all approach to structuring a co-creation process.⁵³ Selecting a foundation to build upon, drawing on previous co-creation practices,⁵⁴ or collaborating with the target group or professionals experienced with the target group⁵⁵ can help determine the number, timing and objectives of sessions. Various planning models and tools, often adopting a similar stepwise approach, are available to guide planning. Examples include planning models like the Behaviour Change Wheel^{14,56–58} or Intervention Mapping,^{59–61} which offer a systematic, structured guide based on theory and evidence for developing an intervention to, for instance, set milestones for co-creation sessions. The case study used a manual on building healthy workspaces in SMEs (permission obtained for use) to structure sessions.^{62,63} It applied a 7-step classic change management process to health in four sessions (2–4 h each): creating a support base and consultation structure; mapping needs, requirements, and opportunities; drawing up and beginning action plan implementation; and evaluating the project and making adjustments. The PRODUCES framework (Table 1) and logic model (Supplementary Material 2) helped align session objectives with the case study’s identified problem, process aim, resources, and outcomes.

In co-creation, the process structure (i.e. session sequence and

objectives) should be flexible to accommodate changes throughout planning and implementation. Stakeholders’ input, for instance, may lead to additional sessions for specific objectives. Additionally, practical considerations can impact the initial plan and evolve based on participants’ needs. The case study’s structure was adapted to accommodate timing, location, and facilitation, resulting in nine shorter (90-min) in-person sessions (Fig. 4). A planning group of employees reviewed the process structure before implementation, and continuous discussions with co-creators refined and tailored sessions and fostered ownership (the full co-creation process, after refinement in three SMEs, is in Supplementary Material 1). It is also important to ensure a smooth transition from solution development to implementation by planning for sustainability. This may involve engaging potential implementers as co-creators, fostering ownership, evaluating feasibility, providing training for implementers, and conducting pilot testing. The case study included live prototyping—a stress test of the solution in real-world conditions—to support this.⁶⁴

3.3.2. Step VI - Select methods for the co-creation sessions

While Step V defines session objectives, Step VI translates these objectives into methods for co-creators to collaborate. Co-creation methods are tools, activities, approaches and techniques employed across the entirety of the co-creation process.⁶⁵ Their careful selection is fundamental to co-creation success, as they can enact its characteristics such as empowerment, participation, collective creativity, collective intelligence, and decision-making.⁶⁶ For example, ‘reverse brainstorming’ encourages collective creativity as groups focus on identifying problems rather than solutions,⁶⁷ and ‘dotmocracy’ allows participants to vote on options using stickers to foster decision-making.⁶⁸

There is no perfect set of methods for co-creation, and predicting their effectiveness in terms of fit or contribution is often difficult.^{53,58} The variety of available methods complicates selection, especially as the desired stakeholder participation level may vary at different stages.^{65,66} However, the diversity of methods applied in co-creation also highlights their adaptability to suit different objectives, groups and contexts.⁶⁹ To

Co-creation Session	Session 1	Session 2	Session 3	Session 4	Session 5	Session 6	Session 7	Live-prototyping	Session 8	Session 9	Aim
Activity Objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Session goal setting <input type="checkbox"/> Introductions & Ground rules <input type="checkbox"/> Explore human capital for health promotion at the company <input type="checkbox"/> Internal change champion <input type="checkbox"/> Group communication channel <input type="checkbox"/> Reflection 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Session goal setting <input type="checkbox"/> Discuss the positives of sitting <input type="checkbox"/> Map the communication possibilities in the company <input type="checkbox"/> Reflection 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Session goal setting <input type="checkbox"/> Knowledge building on SB <input type="checkbox"/> Raising awareness of SB <input type="checkbox"/> Reflection 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Session goal setting <input type="checkbox"/> Map past and current health promotion actions, and their facilitators and barriers <input type="checkbox"/> Mission statement <input type="checkbox"/> Reflection 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Session goal setting <input type="checkbox"/> Map the environmental opportunities inside and outside the company <input type="checkbox"/> Reflection 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Session goal setting <input type="checkbox"/> Brainstorm actions on SB <input type="checkbox"/> Reflection 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Session goal setting <input type="checkbox"/> Check the feasibility of the actions <input type="checkbox"/> Choose and plan a short-term action <input type="checkbox"/> Reflection 	A week of Live Prototyping the short-term action	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Session goal setting <input type="checkbox"/> Evaluate and reflect on the live-prototyping <input type="checkbox"/> Select further actions to implement <input type="checkbox"/> Plan actions for implementing <input type="checkbox"/> Reflection 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Session goal setting <input type="checkbox"/> Continue to plan the actions for implementation <input type="checkbox"/> Discuss the continuation of the action group and initiative <input type="checkbox"/> Reflection 	Co-create with employees to develop a solution for reducing workplace sitting and empower them to lead positive change in their workplace.

	Activity objective	Method	Method description
Session 8	Goal setting for this session	Presentation	Goal setting by summarising the previous workshop and setting out the goals of today’s workshop
	Evaluate and reflect on the action from live-prototyping	(Similar to) Project mid-way evaluation	A bicycle picture is used, and each part has an evaluation question. Each question is asked one at a time, and plenty of time is given to answer. All important points are put on a Post-it and glued to the bicycle by the corresponding part
	Select further actions to implement	Dotmocracy	They get three name tags to vote on action from the previous feasibility exercise. The actions with the most votes are discussed, and decisions are jointly made about how many and which actions to take forward to action planning
	Plan the actions for implementation	Action planning in groups Group discussion	They decide on the timing for implementing the actions together, visualising it on a timeline, and assign a responsible person for the action. Next, they are divided into groups and they work on their preferred action. They plan the actions using a template to describe the objectives, timing, distribution of tasks, resources and evaluation of the action. Afterwards, they present the action plan to the whole group and discuss and improve the plans together.
	Reflecting on the session	Co-creator evaluation form	Reflective evaluation sheet probing the co-creators to think what the next workshops should look like to reach the set goal; using the Emoticon Score Method (‘smiley score’) to evaluate co-creators perception of the usefulness of the workshop and whether they felt heard and part of the workshop; and room for any other comments and feedback

Note. *SB = Sedentary behaviour; A supplementary file detailing the refined co-creation process, developed after applying the initial structure and methods across three UK workplaces consecutively, is provided to ensure transparency and replicability of the co-creation efforts described in the case study.

Fig. 4. Structuring session sequences and objectives for the case study’s co-creation process (Step V) and the alignment of methods to these objectives (Step VI).

navigate this variety, several suggestions can be provided. First, source from academic literature, such as systematic overviews of methods used in co-creation,⁶⁹ and grey literature, like participatory research or facilitation websites.^{70,71} The case study selected methods from the manual used to structure the co-creation sessions,^{62,63} supplemented by grey and academic sources and expert input (Supplementary Material 1). Second, session objectives (Step V) should guide method selection, as illustrated in Fig. 4. For example, for the objective to improve SB knowledge, the case study replaced a broad health knowledge method from the manual with a targeted plenary presentation on SB and its risks as they are often poorly understood,⁷² followed by a quiz to engage co-creators. Third, consider the co-creators' needs and specific context to focus your search. Ideally, stakeholders are involved in method selection to ensure alignment with their interests.⁶⁵ Fourth, fun and creative methods can foster stronger relationships and enhance session efficiency.^{11,35,51} Finally, frameworks like the Co-Creation Rainbow (a tool for articulating the impact of methods on the co-creation process) can match methods to participation levels and co-creation characteristics.⁶⁶ These recommendations offer initial direction on selecting co-creation methods, as detailed guidance in the literature is lacking.^{53,69}

3.4. Section 4 - Plan evaluation

3.4.1. Step VII - Incorporate evaluation

Evaluation should be incorporated early during co-creation planning to ensure it is seamlessly integrated.⁷³ Since no standard co-creation process exists,⁵⁰ it is crucial to define what constitutes 'success' and 'meaningful outcomes' (step IV) for the initiative.⁷⁴ This helps identify and prioritise key evaluation questions.^{75,76}

Planning the evaluation involves selecting the evaluation type(s) (e.g., process vs. effect), setting objectives, choosing methods, participants and timing, and determining stakeholders' roles in the evaluations.^{73,77} Process evaluation is vital for both the co-creation process and solution. Researchers often evaluate participation, context, co-creators' experiences, and impact.⁵⁰ Currently, no process evaluation framework fully captures elements essential to co-creation, like active collaboration, facilitation, and levels of participation.⁵⁰ The case study evaluated co-creators' participation, experiences, and the continuity of the action group after sessions. Following a three-month implementation phase, a focus group gathered co-creators' perspectives on strengths and weaknesses of the co-creation process and solution implementation. Furthermore, the logic model (Supplementary Material 2) served as the framework for evaluating the co-creation process and the co-created solution's impact on health outcomes in the case study. Self-reported workplace SB was measured before the co-creation sessions and after the three-month implementation phase.

Formative evaluation is also key for co-creation, ensuring continuous improvement of the co-creation process.^{3,50} In the case study, this involved co-creators' and facilitators' reflections after each session and insight from interviews with co-creators about their experience.³⁵ Although challenging, participatory evaluation, which engages stakeholders in the evaluation process, can enhance the relevance and comprehensiveness of the evaluation.^{50,77} Simple approaches provide a starting point, like reflecting with stakeholders on outcomes or evaluation methods beforehand.⁵⁰ Traditional evaluation methods (e.g., surveys) are useful, but creative methods like collage or creative writing, can also ensure a thorough evaluation while leaving participants with a positive experience.⁷⁸ Ultimately, the evaluation plan should be clearly outlined yet flexible, allowing for emergent issues to be incorporated.⁷⁶

4. Discussion

This article provides a structured and accessible roadmap to co-creation planning in public health, supported by examples of a research case study and established evidence base of co-creation

literature. Co-creation can be 'messy' due to its continuously evolving nature, with researchers facing challenges such as unclear objectives complicating facilitation,⁵¹ reliance on experience rather than systematic approaches to structuring the co-creation process and method selection,^{53,69} significant time and resource demands;²⁷ and unsuitable process evaluation frameworks for co-creation.⁵⁰ Practical hurdles, like securing ethics approvals and funding, also hinder stakeholder involvement during the initial planning phase.^{11,79} Guidance on planning co-creation initiatives can help navigate these complexities, especially for public health researchers new to co-creation.¹¹ Extensive preparation, as demonstrated by the case study's eight-month planning phase (including preparing materials and ethical requirements), helps prevent superficial efforts^{53,80} and supports the flexibility required to adapt to changing circumstances.⁵¹ This roadmap emphasises the need to validate a co-creation approach with stakeholders and includes the PRODUCES framework to ensure project clarity. It provides guiding questions to determine whom to involve and emphasises diversity and power dynamics.^{3,24} The roadmap also stresses assessing resources and defining outcomes to ensure viability and feasibility. Additionally, it offers guidance on structuring co-creation processes, selecting methods, and preparing for evaluation.

A key strength of the roadmap is its practical step-by-step and evidence-based approach, grounded in an established evidence base of co-creation literature, a real-world research case study, and co-creation expert input. It results in a detailed, context-specific protocol plan that promotes systematic development and replicability of co-creation initiatives in public health research.³ While the roadmap aims to be applicable to other public health research, its development was based on planning and running a specific case study in the context of workplace health promotion in the UK. However, the development was supplemented by existing literature on co-creation in public health more broadly and refined by researchers experienced in planning and implementing multiple co-creation initiatives, strengthening its validity. Since each context and project is unique, local adaptations and considerations (e.g. ethical factors) will be required. Whilst challenging, future research should also prioritise early stakeholder involvement by fostering connections before projects start and addressing stakeholder-identified questions. It is vital to adjust decisions based on stakeholder needs and ensure their views shape outputs from the beginning.¹¹ As the case study lacked stakeholder involvement during planning, this limited our ability to reflect on its impact as part of the roadmap. This future addition may lead to enhanced guidance for planning co-creation that fully embraces stakeholder involvement. Whilst the roadmap is a much-needed tool for supporting co-creation planning, it does not guarantee a successful project or outcomes. This will also depend on factors like effective facilitation and conflict management, which require ongoing attention during implementation.¹⁰ The roadmap's utility will ultimately be determined through future applications, revealing its strengths and areas for improvement across diverse public health challenges and contexts.

Author statements

Ethical approval

Ethical approval for the case study was granted by the Glasgow Caledonian University Research Ethics Committee (approval number: HLS/PSWAHS/21/229).

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Competing interests

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Patients and/or public involvement

Patients and/or the public were not involved in this study.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

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